

COMPLEX COMPOUNDS OF MANGANESE (IV) WITH BIGUANIDES

BY MANOJ MOFAN RAY AND PRIVADARANJAN RAY

Tetrapositive manganese has been found to form cationic complexes with biguanide ligands in which the nitrogen atoms function as donor atoms. These, we believe, represent the first cationic complexes of Mn^{IV} to be reported. $[(OH)_2 Mn (BigH)_2] (OH)_2$ (where BigH is a molecule of biguanide) has been prepared in a variety of ways, e.g., by reduction of Mn^{VII} by ether and/or biguanide, and by oxidation of Mn^{II} with air, hydrogen peroxide or sodium persulphate. Starting from this complex base, a series of salts, namely, nitrate, sulphate, chromate, phosphate, oxalate, iodate and fluoberyllate, has been isolated and studied. Conductivity measurements in aqueous solution show that the complex nitrate dissociates as a bi-univalent salt with slight hydrolysis in dilute state. The valency of manganese in these complexes has been determined by oxidimetric titrations both against sodium thiosulphate (iodometry) and ferrous ammonium sulphate solutions. The corresponding dihydroxo manganese^{IV} ethylenedibiguanide base, $[(OH)_2 Mn^{IV} Et(Big)_2] \cdot 1.5H_2O$, has also been prepared in a similar manner.

The unusually low magnetic moments (2.0–2.5 μ_B) of these complexes, an appreciable rise of the moment value of the complex nitrate in solution and a linear decrease in the effective Bohr magneton value of the solid nitrate from room temperature (300°K) down to 140°K indicate that they may be regarded as penetration or inner-level complexes with d^2sp^3 hybrid bonds with development of some antiferromagnetism, due possibly to metal-metal linkages in the solid state.

The tetrapositive manganese compounds with the single exception of MnO_2 are extremely unstable, at any rate in solution, partly because of the readiness with which they hydrolyse with precipitation of the insoluble manganese dioxide and partly because they are easily reduced by oxidisable substances present. They may, however, be stabilised by complex formation. With its much stronger electronegative character, tetrapositive manganese has relatively poor tendency to form complexes, and in fact, only a few of these like halogeno, cyano, iodato and oxalato complexes are described in the literature.

The halogeno complexes of Mn^{IV} are usually of octahedral type, M_2MnX_6 . These are represented by the hexafluorides, M_2MnF_6 (Weinland and Lauestein, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1899, 20, 40; Bellucci, *Atti R. Accad. Lincei*, 1923, ii, 22, 579; Huss and Klein, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1950, 262, 25; Bode, Jønsen and Bandte, *Angew. Chem.*, 1953, 65, 304), the pentafluorides, $MMnF_5$ (Sharpe and Wolfe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 798) and the hexachlorides M_2MnCl_6 (Weinland and Dinkelacker, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1908, 60, 173; Olsson, *Arkiv Kem. Min. Geol.*, 1924, 9, No. 10, 5). A series of complex iodates $M_2 Mn(IO_3)_6$ has been described by Berg (*Compt. rend.*, 1899, 128, 674). Yakimach (*ibid.*, 1930, 190, 681) obtained a complex cyanide of composition $K_4Mn(CN)_6$ in the form of red crystals, which hydrolysed almost immediately in water and was decomposed by concentrated acids as also on keeping in alcohol. It might as well be represented as a crystal aggregate of $K_2[Mn(CN)_6]$ and 2KCN, since the covalency of manganese is usually limited to six. The oxalato complex of tetrapositive manganese,

$K_2[Mn(C_2O_4)_2(OH)_2] \cdot 2H_2O$, reported by Cartledge and Ericks (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 2069), decomposes rapidly at room temperature and is stable only in the cold and in the absence of light. In aqueous solution it readily changes into trioxalato manganate (III). The crystals are reported to be of two colours, green and orange, and are believed to represent the *cis-trans* isomeric modifications. The dark red colour formed, when freshly precipitated manganese dioxide dissolves in alkaline tellurate, is reported to be due to a manganese^{IV} tellurate compound of unknown constitution (Tourky, Issa and Hewaidy, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1957, 16, 151).

These complexes are all of anionic character, and no cationic complexes of tetrapositive manganese have yet been reported. Besides, manganese in its higher oxidation states has not been known to show any perceptible affinity for combination with nitrogen. Recently, however, we have succeeded in isolating a series of cationic tetrapositive manganese complexes with the metal atom linked to the nitrogen atoms of ligands like biguanide and ethylenedibiguanide.

In a previous paper (this *issue*, p. 595) during the preparation of manganese^{III} biguanide base, an orange-red solution was obtained from which the complex tetrapositive manganese base, $[(OH)_2Mn^{IV}(BigH)_2](OH)_2$ separated in the form of bright red crystals. The same compound can be more conveniently obtained by treating a strongly alkaline solution of an excess of biguanide with potassium permanganate either in the presence or absence of ether. Potassium permanganate is reduced *in situ* by ether or/and by a portion of biguanide, first to the green manganate and finally to tetrapositive manganese which is immediately complexed by the excess of biguanide. A third method for its preparation is based on the oxidation of a strongly alkaline mixture of biguanide and manganous sulphate with hydrogen peroxide or sodium persulphate. From the complex base the corresponding nitrate was prepared, and from the latter other salts like the sulphate, chromate, phosphate, oxalate, iodate and fluoberyllate were obtained by metathesis with the appropriate alkali salts. The nitrate in aqueous solution dissociates into three ions, as might be expected, with an equivalent conductivity of about 148 mhos (vide Table II). The variation of λ_{∞} -value with dilution indicates that the complex suffers slight hydrolysis:

The mobility of the complex ion was found to be 77.1 approx., the conductance of nitrate ion being 71.4.

The complex base of tetrapositive manganese with ethylenedibiguanide, $[(OH)_2Mn^{IV}-Et(Big)_2] \cdot 1.5H_2O$ (where $Et(Big)_2$ = a molecule of ethylenedibiguanide), was prepared by oxidising a mixture of an alkaline solution of the dibiguanide and manganous sulphate with sodium persulphate. The substance forms sparingly soluble reddish brown crystals which appear violet under the microscope. The same product is formed when an alkaline solution of the dibiguanide is treated with a solution of potassium permanganate. All attempts to prepare the corresponding salts were unsuccessful.

FIG. 1

Microphotograph of the crystals of Dihydroxo
Manganese (IV) bis-biguanide dihydrate.

The valency state of manganese in these complexes has been determined by oxidimetric titrations both against sodium thiosulphate (iodometry) and ferrous sulphate solutions. Their magnetic moments, which were expected to substantiate the titrimetric results, however, present some interesting features, as is evident from the following values.

Magnetic moments of Mn^{IV} biguanide complexes.

Substance.	Temp.	Magnetic moment. (μ_B).
X (OH) ₂	30.0°	2.49
X (NO ₃) ₂	29.2°	2.05
X (SO ₄) ₂ . 4.5H ₂ O	29.8°	2.31
X (HPO ₄) ₂ . 1.5H ₂ O	29.6°	2.38
X (C ₂ O ₄) ₂ . 0.5H ₂ O	29.8°	2.25
X (CrO ₄) ₂ . 3H ₂ O	29.6°	2.00
X (IO ₃) ₂ . 2H ₂ O	25.0°	2.20
[(OH) ₂ Mn ^{IV} Bt (Big) ₂]. 1.5H ₂ O	29.2°	2.50

X denotes [(OH)₂ Mn^{IV} (BigH)₂].

It should be mentioned that since Mn⁴⁺-ion contains three 3d electrons (all unpaired) there are two vacant 3d orbitals available for bond formation. Magnetic moment would therefore provide no basis for distinguishing between ionic and covalent bonds, since both types of binding would leave three unpaired electrons and, hence, would give the same moment value. The magnetic moments of manganese (IV) compounds, as are available in the literature, viz., K₂MnF₆ ($\mu_B = 3.88$; Wiedemann, *Ann. Physik u. Chem.*, 1887, **32**, 452), K₂MnCl₆ ($\mu_B = 3.89$; Bhatnagar *et al.*, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1939, **10A**, 150), K₂Mn(IO₃)₆ ($\mu_B = 3.82$; Goldenberg, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1940, **36**, 847) are in close agreement with the predicted value of 3.87 Bohr magnetons. A value of $\mu_B = 2.79$ for K₂[Mn^{IV} (C₂O₄)₂ (OH)₂] reported by Grey (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **68**, 605) is, however, of doubtful significance; for the measurement of its magnetic susceptibility was made at 30°, while it is stated in the original paper (Cartledge and Ericks, *loc. cit.*) that the compound decomposes rapidly at room temperature. The observed reduction in the moment value of the biguanide complexes, the purity of which there is no reason to doubt, seems to indicate that the unpaired electrons in the 3d orbitals fail to behave normally. The discrepancy observed in the case of MnO₂ ($\mu_B = 2.86$; Grey, *loc. cit.*) has been accounted for by assuming that secondary cation to cation bonds are formed through the overlapping of inter-axial orbitals in the crystal lattice of MnO₂. An interaction of this type would naturally deplete the unpaired electrons of Mn^{IV} ions and, hence, would lower the magnetic moment. The discrepancy observed in the manganese^{IV} biguanide complexes, noted above, must be due to some mechanism similar to that of MnO₂. It is tantamount to saying that metallic bonds are formed, as has been suggested in the case of some compounds of rhenium, a congener of manganese (Schuth and Kleim, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1934, **220**, 193; Sen and Rây, *this Journal*, 1953, **30**, 171). Even in the case of oxide, sulphide, selenide and telluride of bivalent manganese, moment values (2.8–3.8 μ_B at room temperature) very much lower than the theoretical value of 5.9 Bohr magnetons, have been reported, which suggests the

formation of metallic bonds. This is further supported by the fact that their moment values increase with increasing temperature, as the break-up of metal-metal bonds would require. The formation of similar metallic bonds in the case of manganese (IV) biguanide complexes also is further supported by the observation that the μ_0 value of 2.05 of the solid complex nitrate rises to 3.14 in solution, which approaches the theoretical value of 3.87 for quadrivalent manganese. Obviously, the metallic bonds break up in solution. A measurement of the temperature variation of the susceptibility of the solid complex nitrate has furnished additional evidence for this assumption. A linear decrease in the effective Bohr magneton value from the room temperature (300°K) down to 140°K, contrary to Curie-Weiss law, has been observed (vide Fig. 2). From a consideration of their physical and chemical behaviour they may therefore be regarded as penetration or inner-level octahedral complexes due to d^2sp^1 hybrid bonds, with development of metal-metal linkages in the solid crystalline state.

EXPERIMENTAL

Dihydroxo Manganese^{IV} bis-Biguanide Dihydrate

A. Reaction with Potassium Permanganate.—A solution of $KMnO_4$ (0.8 g. in 25 c.c. of water) was added dropwise with constant stirring to that of biguanide acid sulphate (5.5 g. in 75 c.c. of 4% NaOH solution). The colour of the permanganate first changes to green (manganate) and finally to dark orange-red. The reduction of permanganate is slow to begin with and gradually becomes rapid. The resulting dark orange-red solution, along with some crystals that separated, was cooled in an ice-bath for about an hour. The mixture was then filtered in a sintered glass crucible and the crystals were washed with ice-cold water. These were sucked dry on the pump and kept in a vacuum desiccator over $CaCl_2$ and KOH. The next day the crystals were taken out and kept in air, free from carbon dioxide, to acquire a constant weight; yield 1.2 g., representing about 75% of the manganese in the permanganate used.

The first crop of the compound which separated immediately in quantities was made up of fine crystals. The mother-liquor on being cooled in an ice-bath deposited a second crop of lustrous needles. The best-sized crystals were obtained by allowing the solution to evaporate slowly in air at room temperature (vide microphotograph, Fig. 1).

The compound has also been prepared from manganous sulphate and biguanide sulphate by oxidation with hydrogen peroxide or sodium persulphate in alkaline medium.

B. Oxidation with Hydrogen Peroxide.—Biguanide acid sulphate (7 g.), dissolved in 8% NaOH solution (50 c.c.) was filtered by suction and the filtrate collected in a flask. A solution of manganous sulphate $MnSO_4 \cdot 4H_2O$ (1 g. in 10 c.c. of water) was added to it, when manganous hydroxide was precipitated. The mixture was cooled in an ice-bath to 10°–15°; 4 c.c. of '20 vol.' hydrogen peroxide was slowly added in portions, while briskly shaking the flask and its contents. The flask was then taken out of the ice-bath and shaken frequently until a dark red solution was obtained. This was filtered by suction immediately. The dark red crystals of the substance separated in quantities on cooling the filtrate in ice for about an hour. These were filtered, washed and dried as described before; yield 1.3 g.

C. *Oxidation with Sodium Persulphate*.—To a cooled solution of biguanide acid sulphate (7 g.) in 8% NaOH solution (50 c.c.) was added dropwise with stirring a solution of manganous sulphate (1 g.) and sodium persulphate (3 g.) in 20 c.c. of water. At the end of the addition the bright red solution was filtered and the filtrate was cooled in ice for about an hour; yield 1.3 g.

{Found: Mn, 16.82, 16.84; O (active), 4.90; N, 43.06; H₂O (by loss at 90°), 11.10. [(OH)₂Mn^{IV}(BigH)₂](OH)₂ requires Mn, 16.90; O (active), 4.92; N, 43.07; H₂O, 11.08%}. {Found (for the vacuum-dried sample): O (active), 5.47. Found (for the sample dried at 90°): O (active), 5.53. Calc. for the dehydrated sample [(OH)₂Mn^{IV}(Big)₂]: O (active), 5.54%}. Oxidimetric titration indicated that the substance suffered partial decomposition at 100°.

The product forms dark red crystals, sparingly soluble in water, giving an orange-red solution. The aqueous solution is alkaline to litmus ($p_H \sim 8$) and is quite stable at room temperature. The solution remains clear for several hours after which it turns turbid due to the separation of manganese dioxide. On keeping in vacuum or by heating at 90°, the compound loses two molecules of water. At higher temperature slow decomposition sets in. The colour of the dehydrated sample is dark chocolate-red. On exposure to air it regains its original weight and colour.

Magnetic Susceptibility: $\chi_g = 7.435 \times 10^{-6}$; $\chi_M = 2416 \times 10^{-6}$; diamagnetic correction = $+ 123 \times 10^{-6}$; χ_M (cor.) = 2539×10^{-6} ; μ_n (effective) = 2.49 (30°).

Dihydroxo Manganese^{IV} bis-Biguanidinium Nitrate

The complex base (1 g.) was suspended in cold water (100 c.c.) in which it partially dissolved. Dilute acetic acid was added dropwise to it with stirring until a dark reddish brown solution (p_H 4–6) was obtained. It was filtered from any residual impurities. To the clear filtrate a solution of potassium nitrate (5 g. in 20 c.c. of water) was added when a flocculent precipitate was obtained. This was allowed to stand in an ice-bath. The precipitate gradually became crystalline and settled down. The crystals were filtered, washed and dried as usual. {Found: Mn 13.47, 13.33; O (active), 3.89, 3.90; N, 42.2; NO₃, 31.06. [(OH)₂Mn^{IV}(BigH)₂](NO₃)₂ requires Mn, 13.23; O (active), 3.85; N, 40.49; NO₃, 29.88%}.

The product forms dark chocolate (almost black) shining crystals. It is readily soluble in water, giving a reddish brown faintly acid solution. Measurement of the conductivity values indicates that the complex is fairly stable in solution for 2–3 hours, but slightly hydrolyses in dilute solutions.

Magnetic Susceptibility: (A) *In the solid state*.— $\chi_g = 3.832 \times 10^{-6}$; $\chi_M = 1591 \times 10^{-6}$; diamagnetic correction = $+ 134.8 \times 10^{-6}$; χ_M (cor.) = 1725.8×10^{-6} ; μ_n (effective) = 2.05 (29.2°).

(B). *In solution*.— χ_g (solution) = -0.7092×10^{-6} ($C_{\text{solution}} = 0.377$ g./50 g. of water); χ_g (solid) = 9.378×10^{-6} ; $\chi_M = 3892 \times 10^{-6}$; χ_M (cor.) = 4027×10^{-6} ; μ_n (effective) = 3.14 (31°).

Study of the Variation of Magnetic Susceptibility with Temperature.—A modified Curie balance (Dutta Ray, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1956, 30, 167) and a liquid air cryostat were used to determine accurately the value of the susceptibility of the sample at room temperature (300°K) by comparison with that of chrome potassium alum crystal, standardised against a standard NiCl₂ solution. The magnetic force on the sample, mounted at the end of the horizontal balance-arm and placed in a vertical magnetic field with a horizontal gradient, was balanced accurately by twisting the vertical quartz fibre from which the balance beam is suspended. The forces at the other constant temperatures down to 140°K, were then measured, retaining all other conditions, e.g., suspension, magnetic field etc., the same as at the room temperature. The results of measurement are shown in Fig. 2 and Table I.

FIG. 2

TABLE I

Temp.	$\chi_M \times 10^6$.	χ_M (cor.) $\times 10^6$.	μ_B (effective).
300° K	1517.2	1652	1.995
260°	1640.2	1775	1.931
220°	1843.2	1978	1.874
180°	2151.2	2286	1.818
160°	2377.2	2512	1.796
140°	2657.2	2792	1.768

Conductivity Measurements.—Solutions of the complex nitrate in different dilutions were made with conductivity water. The conductance of these solutions was measured in a conductivity cell, whose cell constant was determined previously. The equivalent conductivity at infinite dilution was calculated from Walden's formula,

$$\lambda_{\infty} = \lambda_v (1 + 0.692 \times n_1 n_2 \times v^{-1}),$$

where n_1 and n_2 are the valencies of the ions. The results are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Cell constant = 1.503. Temp. = 29°.

Dilution in litres (v).	Conductance $\bar{\kappa}$ (μ).	Equivalent conductivity (λ_v).	Equivalent conductivity at infinite dilution (λ_∞).
64	0.1×10^4 mho	96.2	112.8
128	5.4×10^2	102.0	114.5
256	3.2×10^2	123.1	133.8
512	1.73×10^2	133.1	141.2
1024	0.93×10^2	142.3	148.5

The variation of λ_∞ -value with dilution signifies progressive hydrolysis.*Dihydroxo Manganese^{IV} bis-Biguanidinium Sulphate*

The complex base (1 g.), mixed with cold water (20 c.c.), was treated with dilute nitric acid (3 N) dropwise until a clear solution was obtained (p_n 4-6). The solution was filtered. To the filtrate 5% ammonium sulphate solution was added dropwise with stirring until a precipitate just appeared. The mixture was cooled in ice for half an hour. The shining silky crystals of the complex sulphate separating were filtered, washed and dried as usual. The same product was obtained by treating an aqueous solution of the pure complex nitrate with ammonium sulphate; yield 0.9 g. {Found: Mn, 11.69, 11.75; O (active), 3.43; N, 30.14; SO₄, 20.35; H₂O (by loss at 90°), 17.18. [(OH)₂ Mn^{IV} (BigH)₂]SO₄ · 4.5H₂O requires Mn, 11.75; O (active), 3.42; N, 29.91; SO₄, 20.51; H₂O, 17.31%}. [Found for the sample dehydrated at 90°: O (active), 4.09. Calc.: O (active), 4.13%].

The product ordinarily forms snuff-coloured crystalline powder, sparingly soluble in water, giving a light-yellow, faintly acid solution. The compound is fairly stable at room temperature in the dry state.

Magnetic Susceptibility: $\chi_g = 4.268 \times 10^{-6}$; $\chi_m = 1997 \times 10^{-8}$; diamagnetic correction = + 195.5 $\times 10^{-6}$; χ_m (cor.) = 2192.5 $\times 10^{-8}$; μ_n (effective) = 2.314 (29.8°).

Dihydroxo Manganese^{IV} bis-Biguanidinium Hydrogen Phosphate

To the filtered solution of the complex nitrate (1 g.) in cold water (20 c.c.) a solution of disodium hydrogen phosphate (1 g. in 10 c.c. of water) was added dropwise with stirring until a slight turbidity appeared. The mixture was cooled in ice for about half an hour. The crystals of the complex phosphate separating were filtered, washed and dried as usual; yield 0.9 g.

For the estimation of total manganese and phosphate, the complex was decomposed by digesting with dilute alkali on the water-bath and filtered. The residual manganese dioxide was dissolved in HCl (dil.) and manganese was precipitated as MnNH₄PO₄. From the combined filtrate and washings phosphoric acid was precipitated as MgNH₄PO₄. {Found: Mn, 13.22; O (active), 3.88, 3.85; PO₄, 22.44. [(OH)₂Mn^{IV}-(BigH)₂](HPO₄) · 1.5H₂O requires Mn, 13.26; O (active), 3.86; PO₄, 22.92%}. It resembles the sulphate in properties.

Magnetic Susceptibility: $\chi_g = 5.217 \times 10^{-6}$; $\chi_m = 2160 \times 10^{-8}$; diamagnetic correction = + 159 $\times 10^{-6}$; χ_m (cor.) = 2319 $\times 10^{-8}$; μ_n (effective) = 2.38 (29.6°).

Dihydroxo Manganese^{IV} bis-Biguanidinium Oxalate

This was obtained as a chocolate-brown crystalline precipitate from a solution of the complex nitrate by adding a solution of sodium oxalate.

For analysis, the sample was decomposed by boiling with dilute alkali. Precipitated manganese dioxide was filtered off and in the filtrate oxalic acid was estimated by titration with permanganate as usual. Manganese was estimated as MnSO_4 . {Found: Mn, 14.07; O (active), 4.12; $(\text{COO})_2$, 22.2. $[(\text{OH})_2 \text{Mn}^{\text{IV}} (\text{BigH})_2](\text{COO})_2 \cdot 0.5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Mn, 14.16; O (active), 4.12; $(\text{COO})_2$, 22.69%}.

Magnetic Susceptibility: $\chi_g = 4.989 \times 10^{-8}$; $\chi_M = 1936 \times 10^{-8}$; diamagnetic correction = $+ 131 \times 10^{-8}$; χ_M (cor.) = 2067×10^{-8} ; μ_n (effective) = 2.247 (29.8°).

Dihydroxo Manganese^{IV} bis-Biguanidinium Chromate

This was prepared by double decomposition of the complex nitrate with potassium chromate.

For the estimation of total manganese and chromium, the complex was decomposed with dilute alkali. The precipitated manganese dioxide was filtered. In the filtrate chromate was determined in the usual way by titration against ferrous ammonium sulphate. The residue was dissolved in HCl and manganese was precipitated as MnNH_4PO_4 . {Found: Mn, 11.80; CrO_4 , 25.27; active oxygen (total), 8.71; N, 30.01%. $[(\text{OH})_2 \text{Mn}^{\text{IV}} (\text{BigH})_2]\text{CrO}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Mn, 11.94; CrO_4 , 25.16; active oxygen (total), 8.68; N, 30.37%}.

The product forms snuff-coloured crystals sparingly soluble in water, giving a light yellow solution.

Magnetic Susceptibility: $\chi_g = 3.561 \times 10^{-8}$; $\chi_M = 1642 \times 10^{-8}$; diamagnetic correction = $+ 116 \times 10^{-8}$; χ_M (cor.) = 1758×10^{-8} ; μ_n (effective) = 2.07 (29.6°).

Dihydroxo Manganese^{IV} bis-Biguanidinium Iodate

The complex base (1 g.) was mixed with cold water (50 c.c.) and the mixture was treated dropwise with dilute acetic acid until a dark reddish brown solution (p_H 4-6) was obtained. It was filtered to remove any residual impurity. To the clear filtrate an almost saturated solution of potassium iodate (2 g. in 25 c.c. of water) was added with stirring, when the solution became slightly hazy. The mixture was cooled in an ice-bath for about an hour. The small chocolate-coloured glistening crystals that separated were filtered, washed with ice-cold water and dried as usual.

Iodate was estimated by reducing the sample with sulphur dioxide in sulphuric acid medium to iodide which was then precipitated as AgI. {Found: Mn, 8.10; active oxygen (total), 16.39; IO_3 , 51.53; H_2O (by loss in vacuum), 5.77. $[(\text{OH})_2 \text{Mn}^{\text{IV}} (\text{BigH})_2](\text{IO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Mn, 8.12; active oxygen (total), 16.54; IO_3 , 51.70; H_2O , 5.32%}.

Magnetic Susceptibility: $\chi_g = 2.665 \times 10^{-8}$; $\chi_M = 1804 \times 10^{-8}$; diamagnetic correction = $+ 199.8 \times 10^{-8}$; χ_M (cor.) = 2003.8×10^{-8} ; μ_n (effective) = 2.195 (25°).

Dihydroxo Manganese^{IV} bis-Biguanidinium Fluoberyllate

The complex fluoberyllate was prepared by treating a solution of the complex nitrate with a concentrated solution of ammonium fluoberyllate and cooling the mixture in an ice-bath. The substance on qualitative analysis was found to contain Be and F, giving characteristic reactions of BeF_4^{2-} ion. { Found : Mn, 12.42 ; O (active), 3.60. $[(\text{OH})_2 \text{Mn}^{\text{IV}} (\text{BigH})_2] \text{BeF}_4 \cdot 3.5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Mn, 12.51 ; O (active), 3.64% }.

The product forms fairly soluble cinnamon-coloured crystals.

Dihydroxo Manganese^{IV} Ethylenedibiguanide Hydrate

Ethylenedibiguanidinium sulphate (4 g.) (Chakravarty and Rây, this *Journal*, 1944, 21, 441) was dissolved in 15% NaOH solution (60 c.c.) and filtered. To the filtrate a solution of manganous sulphate (1 g.) and sodium persulphate (3 g.) in 20 c.c of water was added with stirring. A dark reddish brown solution was obtained. This was immediately filtered by suction to remove any precipitated manganese dioxide. The filtrate was then cooled in ice for about half an hour. Reddish brown crystals separating were filtered, washed with ice-cold water and dried in vacuum over CaCl_2 and KOH. { Found : Mn, 16.04 ; O (active), 4.63, 4.67 ; N, 40.56, 40.79. $[(\text{OH})_2 \text{Mn}^{\text{IV}} \cdot \text{Et}(\text{Big})_2] 1.5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Mn, 16.06 ; O (active), 4.67 ; N, 40.94% }.

The product forms reddish brown crystals, sparingly soluble in water, giving a reddish brown solution which reacts alkaline to litmus ($p_n \sim 8$). Addition of alkali salt solution to a solution of the complex, base, acidified with dilute acetic acid, produces an opalescence. The compound is quite stable both in the solid state and in solution at room temperature.

Magnetic Susceptibility : $\chi_g = 7.087 \times 10^{-6}$; $\chi_m = 2423.8 \times 10^{-8}$; diamagnetic correction = $+ 140.2 \times 10^{-8}$; $\chi_m (\text{cor.}) = 2564 \times 10^{-8}$; $\mu_n (\text{effective}) = 2.50 (29.2^\circ)$.

The authors are grateful to Sri S. K. Dutta Ray and Sri A. I. P. Sinha of the Department of Magnetism of this Institute for their help in connection with the measurement of magnetic susceptibility reported in this paper and to Sri Mauindra Nath Dutta, Department of Zoology, University College of Science and Technology, Calcutta, for the microphotograph. The authors take this opportunity of expressing their best appreciation and thanks to Messers American Cyanamide Ltd., Ontario, Canada, for a handsome gift of dicyandiamide for the preparation of biguanides employed in this work.